

Table 2. Effect of percolation and urea fertilizer on micronutrient content of rice plants (60 DT).^a

Urea fertilizer	Micronutrients (ppm)							
	Without percolation				With percolation			
	Zn	Fe	Mn	Cu	Zn	Fe	Mn	Cu
Check	34.6 a	130 a	480 a	6.0 a	22.0 a	165 a	383 ab	4.0 a
Prilled urea 3-split	50.6 b	226 bc	591 bc	10.0 b	38.6 b	260 bc	421 ab	8.0 b
Urea mudball	53.0 b	240 c	580 bc	8.0 ab	39.3 b	256 bc	378 ab	6.0 ab
Urea supergranule	58.3 b	223 bc	651 c	9.3 b	35.3 b	231 b	343 a	7.3 b
Sulfur-coated urea	38.6 a	176 ab	545 ab	6.0 a	35.6 b	286 c	458 b	6.3 b
Interaction ^b	(PXU)**	(PXU)**	(PXU)**	(PXU)**	(PXU)**	(PXU)**	(PXU)**	(PXU)**
CV (%)	12.9	14.1	9.7	19.2	12.9	14.1	9.7	19.2

^a In a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at $P = 0.05$. ^b** = significant at $P = 0.01$, P = percolation, U = urea material.

Fertilizer trials in West Bengal

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We compared farmer fertilizer use levels with recommended levels in Purulia, West Bengal, in 1981 kharif. Soil characteristics at 6 demonstration sites varied from

pH 4.8 to 6.8, 0.28 to 0.83% organic matter, 5.5 to 38.1 kg available P/ha, and 116.2 to 160.5 kg available K/ha.

IET1444 (Rasi) was transplanted in rainfed fields at 4 fertilizer levels: farmer level of 20.0-4.4-8.3 kg NPK/ha; treatment 1, 27.0-7.0-12.4 kg NPK/ha; treatment 2, 45.0-8.4-20.8 kg NPK/ha; and treatment 3, 55.0-9.7-27.4 kg NPK/ha.

Treatment 3 yielded highest – 3.6 t/ha — (see table) but treatment 2, which yielded 3.4 t/ha, gave the highest benefit-cost ratio, 10.5. Economic analysis of treatments and yields showed that investing an extra \$11.23 to \$39.43/ha could increase returns from \$100.23 to \$311.62/ha. □

Economic analysis of added NPK compared to farmer fertilizer management level in Purulia, West Bengal.

Treatment	Fertilizer rate (kg/ha)			Yield range (t/ha)	Mean yield (t/ha)	Added yield over farmer level (t/ha)	Value of added yield (\$/ha)	Cost of added inputs ^a (\$/ha)	Added profit over farmer level (\$/ha)	Benefit: cost
	N	P	K							
Farmer level	20	4.4	8.3	0.94-1.15	1.07	—	—	—	—	—
1	27	7.0	12.4	1.62-2.05	1.86	0.79	111.46	11.23	100.23	8.9
2 ^b	45	8.4	20.8	3.12-3.65	3.36	2.29	323.01	28.14	294.87	10.5
3	55	9.7	27.4	3.46-3.61	3.56	2.49	351.05	39.43	311.62	7.9

^a Cost/kg of fertilizer – N:\$0.66, P:\$2.00, K:\$0.32; price of paddy/t = \$141.10. ^b Recommended level.

Effect of azolla on the growth and yield of rice plants

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We evaluated azolla as a substitute for urea fertilizer for rice in a pot experiment at the Botanical Garden, University of Dhaka.

Urea was applied at 0, 25, 50, 75, and 100 kg N/ha (see table) with and without azolla. Triple superphosphate and muriate of potash, each at 50 kg/ha, were applied to all treatments except the control. Fresh azolla was inoculated 7 days after transplanting BR3 and incorporated when growth covered the pot, about 2 weeks after inoculation. Treatments were in a

randomized block design with four replications.

Azolla incorporation alone or in combination with urea stimulated rice growth and increased grain yield. Highest yield was 72.3 g/pot with 100 kg N/ha + azolla

(see table). Grain yield was similar for 75 kg N alone and 25 kg N + azolla. Azolla application also increased straw weight. Applying 75 kg N alone or 50 kg N + azolla gave the same straw yield (58 g/pot). □

Effect of azolla on rice grain and straw yield.

Treatment ^a (kg N/ha)	Av no. of grains/hill	Straw yield (g)	Grain yield (g)
No chemical fertilizer	1021	29.3	29.1
TSP + MP alone	1049	29.6	29.9
25	1478	43.0	42.1
50	1631	46.0	46.5
75	1965	58.0	56.0
100	2283	63.0	62.8
Azolla	1709	50.0	49.7
25 + azolla	1994	57.0	56.8
50 + azolla	2048	58.0	58.4
75 + azolla	2521	69.5	71.9
100 + azolla	2537	72.0	72.3

^a All treatments except the first have TSP and MP, each at 50 kg/ha.